

Ligand dependent metal-metal interaction in mixed-ligand oxovanadium(IV) complexes with N,O donor ligands

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Mixed-ligand oxovanadium(IV) complexes with two different types of bidentate ligands [one is dinegative O,O donor ligand (viz., glycolic acid, 2-hydroxybenzylalcohol and glycol) and the other is neutral N,N donor ligand (viz., 2,2'-bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline)] have been prepared and characterized by elemental analyses, IR, EPR and UV-Vis spectroscopies. The complexes are paramagnetic and showed subnormal magnetic behaviour ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.01\text{--}1.60$ B.M.) at RT. The V=O stretching frequencies of the complexes indicate the hexa-coordinated environment though only five donor atoms are provided to the vanadium centre and it is explained by considering the formation of bridge through either by alcoholic oxygen or by phenolic oxygen leading to dimerization. The EPR spectra support the dimeric nature of the complexes and indicate that the odd electron of the metal is present in its $3d_{xy}$ orbital. The lower magnetic moment values are explained by considering the overlapping between two $3d_{xy}$ orbitals of the two V^{4+} ions in the dimeric complexes. The complexes display an irreversible oxidation peak in the region 0.49–0.89 V vs Ag/AgCl. μ_{eff} and oxidation peak potential values (E_p^a) are correlated with the basicity of the donor atoms of the ligands.

The study of the chemistry of new complexes of vanadium has become an important area of research because of its involvement in biological systems¹. It is an element with wide range of chemical properties. It is found in the active sites of metalloenzymes² conferring specific functions and controlling their catalytic reactivity. Recent studies indicate that vanadium is also present in the living system and associated with a number of activities e.g., enzyme inhibitory³, mitogenic⁴, antitumorigenic⁵ and insulinomimetic⁶. A number of such metabolic actions appears to be the basic chemical interactions of this metal ion with large and small molecules in biological media. The ligands containing carboxylic/phenolic/alcoholic moieties are of biological relevant^{7–9}. Studies showed that V^V and V^{IV} are the two important oxidation states exist in biological media¹⁰. We are interested here with the V^{IV} motif. This motif has two common coordination numbers-five and -six and because of its hard nature it has good affinity towards N,O donor ligands. This work stems from our interest on the interaction of neighbouring molecules through the vacant position of the metal when its five coordination sites are already blocked by donor atoms¹¹. In this work we have used three simple molecules viz., glycolic acid, 2-hydroxybenzylalcohol and glycol (hereafter, $H_2\text{glyc}$, $H_2\text{hba}$ and $H_2\text{gol}$, respectively) as pri-

mary ligands to provide (O^-, O^-) donor moieties with varying basicity. A few complexes of glycolic acid and glycol with oxovanadium(V) ion either in simple or in mixed-ligand systems have been reported in the literature^{12–17}, but to the best of our knowledge no such study of oxovanadium(IV) ion with these ligands in the mixed-ligand systems have been done. 2,2'-Bipyridine and 1,10-phenanthroline (hereafter, bipy and phen respectively) are used as secondary neutral bidentate N,N donor ligands.

Results and discussion

Dianions of $H_2\text{glyc}$, $H_2\text{hba}$ and $H_2\text{gol}$ (general abbreviation H_2L , where Hs represent the dissociable carboxylic/phenolic/alcoholic protons) provide (O^-, O^-) donor moieties and B ligands provide N,N bidentate chelation in $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{B})].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ complexes. The compounds are not soluble in water and in common organic solvents and most of the compounds are high melting ($>270^\circ$). The analytical data (Table 1) indicate the formation of $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{B})].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ternary complexes but the IR spectral data and magnetic moment values are in favour of their dimeric nature (*vide infra*).

IR spectra, magnetic susceptibility and EPR spectra :

The complexes display strong V=O stretching frequen-

Table 1. Analytical, IR and magnetic moment data for the complexes

Compd [*]	IR (cm ⁻¹) ^a			μ_{eff}^b (B.M.)
	V=O	CO ₂ (asym)	CO ₂ (sym)	
[VO(glyc)(bipy)].2H ₂ O, (1)	983	1623	1322	1.60
[VO(glyc)(phen)].2H ₂ O, (2)	985	1623	1322	1.53
[VO(hba)(bipy)].2H ₂ O, (3)	985	-	-	1.57
[VO(hba)(phen)].2H ₂ O, (4)	952	-	-	1.51
[VO(gol)(bipy)].2H ₂ O, (5)	974	-	-	1.30
[VO(gol)(phen)].2H ₂ O, (6)	970	-	-	1.01

^{*}All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

^aKBr discs. ^bat 298 K.

cies in the region 952–985 cm⁻¹ (Table 1) which is lower for penta-coordination (~1000 cm⁻¹)^{18,19} but compatible with hexa-coordination (<990 cm⁻¹)²⁰⁻²³. The complexes **1** and **2** exhibited two bands near 1322 and 1623 cm⁻¹ due to the symmetric and antisymmetric stretching of the coordinated carboxylate group. The difference between the symmetric and antisymmetric stretches, $\Delta\nu(\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-) - \nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-))$ of the complexes **1** and **2** is greater than 200 cm⁻¹, indicating the monodentate binding of the carboxylate group^{24,25}. Disappearance of the OH stretching frequencies of the phenolic and alcoholic moieties of hba ligand at 3162 and 3444 cm⁻¹ respectively in its complexes **3** and **4**, indicate the coordination of OH groups to V^{IV} with deprotonation. Shifting of the C–O stretching of the phenolic and alcoholic moieties at 1460 and 1260 cm⁻¹ respectively towards the higher frequency in the complexes **3** and **4** by ~65 cm⁻¹ for phenolic C–O and ~16 cm⁻¹ for alcoholic C–O indicates the involvement of the phenolic C–O group in the bridge formation^{11,26}. A sharp band in the region 3400–3450 cm⁻¹ for all the complexes indicate the presence of uncoordinated water molecules^{18,19}.

All the complexes (**1-6**) are paramagnetic and the magnetic moment values ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.01\text{--}1.60$ B.M.) are lower than the expected value for a d^1 system (1.73 B.M.), indicate that antiferromagnetic interaction is operating. The complexes are EPR active. The EPR spectra of complexes (**1-4**) are taken in DMSO at 77 K and a representative spectra is displayed in Fig. 1 and the values of EPR parameters are collected in Table 2. An analysis to data in Table 2 indicates $g_{\parallel} < g_{\perp}$ and $A_{\parallel} \gg A_{\perp}$ relationships, characteristics for an axially compressed d_{xy} configuration^{27,28}.

In spite of our best efforts none of the complexes provided crystals suitable for X-ray work. However, the

Table 2. EPR data of complexes **1-4** at 77 K

Compd.	g_{\parallel} ($10^4 A_{\parallel}/\text{cm}^{-1}$)	g_{\perp} ($10^4 A_{\perp}/\text{cm}^{-1}$)
[VO(glyc)(bipy)].2H ₂ O, (1)	1.931 (173.6)	1.983 (70.0)
[VO(glyc)(phen)].2H ₂ O, (2)	1.937 (172.8)	1.983 (69.3)
[VO(hba)(bipy)].2H ₂ O, (3)	1.937 (172.1)	1.981 (69.3)
[VO(hba)(phen)].2H ₂ O, (4)	1.941 (170.7)	1.981 (68.1)

^aEstimated error in g values : 0.002 and in A values : 3×10^4 cm⁻¹.

EPR spectra can give an important information about the groups coordinated to the metal in the equatorial positions. EPR spectra of the complexes are consistent with the presence of dimeric species in solution (Fig. 1). On the basis of additivity relationship presented by Chasteen²⁹

Fig. 1. X-Band EPR spectra of [VO(hba)(bipy)].2H₂O, **3** in DMSO at 77 K.

with estimated accuracy $\pm 3 \times 10^{-4}$ cm⁻¹, the value of A_{\parallel} can be estimated ($A_{\parallel}^{\text{est}}$) for a specific donor set by the eqn. (1).

$$A_{\parallel}^{\text{est}} = \sum_{i=1}^4 A_{\parallel}, i/4 \quad (1)$$

Two different types of dimeric structures (**I** and **II**) are possible for complexes with one oxo, one bidentate dinegative (O⁻,O⁻) and one neutral bidentate (N,N) donor ligands. In structure **I**, two pyridyl nitrogen atoms of B ligand are in equatorial positions and in structure **II**, one of the two pyridyl nitrogen atoms of B ligand is in

equatorial position.

The $A_{\parallel}^{\text{est}}$ value of complexes **1** and **2** with one carboxylate oxygen, two bridged alcoholic oxygens and one pyridyl nitrogen in the equatorial positions is $175.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and that with two pyridyl nitrogen atoms and two bridged alcoholic oxygens in the equatorial positions is $173.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. So, for complexes **1** and **2** the most probable gross structure is **I**. For complexes **3** and **4** with one alcoholic oxygen, two bridged phenolic oxygens and one pyridyl nitrogen, the $A_{\parallel}^{\text{est}}$ is 171.6 and it is 177.1 for two pyridine nitrogen atoms and two bridged phenolic oxygen atoms in the equatorial positions. So, for complexes **3** and **4**, the most probable structure is as designated by **II** (the superscripts a, c and p denote the alcoholic, carboxylic and phenolic oxygen moieties respectively). The proposed structure **II** for complexes **3** and **4** indicates the dissimilar binding nature of two nitrogen atoms of bipy and phen moieties, because the N atom which is trans to the oxo group, is more weakly bonded than the N atom that is trans to the phenolate or alcoholate O atom. In fact such binding is crystallographically well documented^{21,30}.

An analysis to data in Table 2 reveals that hba ligand slightly decreases the A_{\parallel} value for a given N,N donor ligand compared to glyc ligand and for a given O^-, O^- donor primary ligand phen slightly decreases A_{\parallel} over bipy. As only the equatorial donor atoms (through their basicity) can influence the value of A_{\parallel} , so a higher basic donor atom can decrease the A_{\parallel} value to a greater extent. A plot (Fig. 2) of A_{\parallel} vs $\Sigma \text{p}K_a$ for a particular N,N donor ligand (e.g., phen) with different primary O^-, O^- donor ligand

Fig. 2. Plot of A_{\parallel} vs $\Sigma \text{p}K_a$ of the complexes with phen as secondary ligand.

(e.g., salicylic acid¹¹, glyc and hba) indicates their linear relationship. The calculated $\Sigma \text{p}K_a$ ^{31,32} values are 18.55, 34.55 and 37.2 for salicylic acid, glyc and hba respectively with phen. The magnetic moment value of the complexes (**1-6**) also decreases gradually with the increase of basicity of the ligands. The odd electron as indicated by the EPR spectra is present in $3d_{xy}$ orbital of the metal. Because of the appropriate symmetry of d_{xy} orbitals of metals in these dinuclear complexes a direct overlapping

is possible and this accounts for the observed reduced magnetic moment values. The extent of overlapping increases with the increase of overall basicity of the ligand and explains the order of magnetic moment values **1** > **3** > **5** and **2** > **4** > **6** for two different invariant N,N donor ligands viz., bipy and phen respectively.

Electronic spectra and electrochemistry of the complexes :

The greenish-yellow to red complexes (**1-6**) display three ligand-field transitions in the visible region (Table 3) : 787–850, 514–560 and 430–445 nm due to ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$, ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{1g}$ and ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ transitions respectively³³. The molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) values are comparatively large for *d-d* transitions and this is probably due to the distortion from perfect octahedral geometry as is evident from structures (**I** and **II**).

Table 3. Spectral^a and electrochemical data^{a,b} at 298 K for the complexes

Compd.	UV-Vis	E_p^a (V)
	$\lambda_{\text{max}}/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	
[VO(glyc)(bipy)].2H ₂ O, (1)	840 (59); 525 (48); 430sh (73)	+0.89
[VO(glyc)(phen)].2H ₂ O, (2)	787(12); 514sh (40); 445 (91)	+0.86
[VO(hba)(bipy)].2H ₂ O, (3)	838 (58); 430sh (102)	+0.64
[VO(hba)(phen)].2H ₂ O, (4)	802 (64); 534sh (82); 444 (256)	+0.60
[VO(gol)(bipy)].2H ₂ O, (5)	846 (126); 560 (160); 435 (225)	+0.62
[VO(gol)(phen)].2H ₂ O, (6)	850 (38); 525 (152); 435 (186)	+0.49

^aIn DMSO. ^bAt a Pt disk electrode; supporting electrolyte tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP, ~0.1 M); scan rate 50 mV s⁻¹; refer electrode Ag/AgCl, solute concentration ca. 10⁻³ M; E_p^a = anodic peak potential value; sh = shoulder.

All the oxovanadium(IV) complexes uniformly exhibit an electron irreversible oxidation peak in DMSO solution in the region 0.89–0.49 V vs Ag/AgCl (Table 3). An analysis of the E_p^a (oxidation peak potential) data in Table 3 indicates that it decreases gradually from complex **1-6** and follow the order **1** > **2** > **3** > **4** > **5** > **6**. From the point of view of basicity of the ligands this order is quite expected.

Conclusion :

From this study it is evident that the mixed-ligand complexes containing at least one strong basic moiety (e.g., alcoholate or phenolate) exhibit subnormal magnetic behaviour and this behaviour is explained by considering the V...V interaction through their d_{xy} orbitals leading to dimerization. The other possible mechanism, 'super-exchange' is ruled out as the odd electron is present in the d_{xy} orbital (evident from their EPR spectra). The extent of V...V interaction depends upon the basicity of the

ligands. Both the magnetic susceptibility and the E_p^a values gradually decreases with the increase of overall basicity of the ligands. A closer look at the proposed structures **I** and **II** indicates that the V atom has the tendency to accommodate the more basic donor atoms in its equatorial positions.

Experimental

Materials :

47% Aqueous solution of glycolic acid, 2-hydroxybenzylalcohol, glycol, 2,2'-bipyridine, 1,10-phenanthroline, sodium acetate trihydrate were procured from E. Merck (Germany). $\text{VO}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained from Loba chemical company, India and all other materials were of A.R. grade and were used as received. Tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) was prepared and recrystallised by known procedure³⁴.

Preparation of the metal complexes :

The six complexes reported herein were prepared by the same general method. Details are given for one representative case only.

Glycolic acid (0.076 g, i.e., 0.134 g of 57% aqueous solution of it; 1 mmol), bipy (0.156 g, 1 mmol) and sodium acetate trihydrate (0.272 g, 2 mmol) were dissolved in 25 ml aqueous-ethanol (50% v/v). The mixture was slightly warmed ($\sim 60^\circ$) and then added dropwise aqueous solution (5 ml) of $\text{VO}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.253 g, 1 mmol) to it. The reaction mixture was stirred for 3 h at $\sim 60^\circ$. It was then kept at room temperature. After 2 weeks a greenish yellow product was obtained. It was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and ethanol and then dried over silica gel. yield : 0.1 g (30%). In case of the other two primary ligands, the products were obtained during the reaction time period (~ 3 h).

Physical measurements :

Electronic spectra (in DMSO) were recorded on a Hitachi U-3501 spectrophotomete, IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 782 spectrophotometer and EPR spectra in the X-band on E-112 Century series Varian E-102 Microwave bridge spectrometer. Tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) ($g = 2.0027$) was used to calibrate the EPR spectra. Electrochemical measurements were performed on a EG & G PARC model 270 VERSTAT electrochemical instruments. Electrochemical experiments were performed at 298 K under N_2 atmosphere with a three electrode system. Magnetic susceptibilities were measured using a PAR 155 vibrating sample magnetometer fitted with Walker

Scientific L75 FBAL magnet using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as the calibrant. A Perkin-Elmer CHNS/O analyzer 2400 was employed to obtain microanalytical (C, H, N) data.

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